

SCIENTIFIC VIEWS ON CONDUCTING DISCIPLINARY PROCEEDINGS AND SERVICE INSPECTION

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Annotation: the article presents the essence of conducting a service inspection, which is one of the main stages of internal affairs, the opinions of several scientists and the conclusions of scientific researchers working in the field, based on the noted scientific approaches, the author's personal views on disciplinary proceedings are presented.

Key words: pre-investigation review, service review, scientific views, scientific approaches

Legal procedural proceedings are extensive and are divided into branches of law based on the factual circumstances that arise in different situations. Among these, service audit processes can be included in the scope of various procedural law branches, depending on the existing factual circumstances.

Before analyzing the process of conducting a service audit, it is necessary to pay attention to the details of these concepts.

According to the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word "service" has the meanings of engaging in work or work [1], the word "investigation" has the meanings of learning research, as well as learning whether something is right or wrong [2], and the word "investigation" means a crime has occurred. It means investigating the circumstances, its causes and participants, gathering evidence in a criminal case [3].

From the above definitions, it is possible to understand the processes of inspection and service inspection before the investigation as a set of administrative, disciplinary and procedural processes conducted in order to clarify a situation.

According to the scholars who have researched the topic, conducting a service investigation, which is a form of disciplinary proceedings, may belong to the object of study of several legal disciplines according to the subject of scientific research [4].

In particular, it is the labor right to conduct a service inspection in connection with a disciplinary violation committed during work, an administrative right when it is carried out in connection with some part of the service obligations during the service or other offenses not related to the service, a pre-investigation investigation to determine the signs of a crime, and a crime within the framework of the initiated criminal case. - is an object of procedural law.

Scientists who have scientifically analyzed the field have expressed different opinions about the role of service inspection in the administrative stage. The main one is the opinion expressed by D.N. Bakhrax, according to which the service inspection is the first stage of disciplinary proceedings [5]. M.B. According to Dobrobama, disciplinary action and service review are considered as one process[6].

In order to understand the subject more broadly, based on V.N. Protasov's scientific view, it is possible to make a comparative analysis with the general stages of procedural processes, including:

- detailed study of all factual aspects of the case;
- review of the legal grounds for the situation;
- making a legal decision regarding the situation;
- ensuring the execution of the final decision[7].

At the initial stage, provable cases are clarified with the help of evidence. In

this process, evidence collection and consolidation and evaluation are performed. Clarification of work situations is regulated by laws and regulations. Examples of this include obtaining explanatory letters from the participants in the process, studying documents, inspecting the scene of the incident, things and objects, etc.

In the process of formation of legal frameworks, after clarifying all business situations, a legal evaluation of the situation is given through the law and other regulatory legal frameworks that regulate the activity. After a full legal assessment of the case, a decision on the service review will be made.

Kaplunov A.I. analyzes the stages of conducting a service audit based on a logical approach and divides it as follows [8], in particular:

- initiating a case;
- clarifying the situation and making a decision;
- ensuring execution of the decision.

Also, in the General Military Regulations of the Armed Forces, an explanation is given regarding the process of disciplinary proceedings as a service review and not a service review [9]. Service discussion is a narrow process in its dictionary meaning and practice and does not fully cover case studies. Therefore, it is appropriate to use the term service review in relation to the disciplinary proceedings in the Disciplinary Regulations of the Armed Forces. First, it serves to create a unified approach to organizational and legal issues related to the conduct of disciplinary proceedings in all state civil service and law enforcement agencies.

The lack of a single definition of the concept of service inspection in scientific and legal literature is the reason for different interpretations of this term.

For example, Yu.S. Adushkin described service inspection as a process of notifying authorized entities for decision-making regarding disciplinary violations[10]. From this definition, it can be understood as a procedure for notifying the competent authorities and making a decision regarding service

inspection.

As a result of his research, E.A. Nikonorov interprets service inspection as an administrative-legal institution[11]. A relatively narrower approach can be seen in the development of this definition. The reason is that as a result of studying the procedural processes related to the service inspection above, we can witness that the disciplinary action includes not only administrative law, but also military, criminal, labor and criminal executive rights.

S. E. Channov evaluates the service inspection as a comprehensive, complete, timely set of measures in order to determine whether there is a disciplinary violation in the act committed by the civil servant by the responsible persons of the public service [12]. It can be seen that this definition covers the steps of conducting a service audit relatively comprehensively.

The opinions of N.A. Ovchinnikov regarding the service inspection are similar to the opinions of Yu.S. Adushkin, according to him [13], according to the result of the service inspection, it is necessary to make a decision on the imposition of punishment in a disciplinary procedure or to reject a situation that may damage the reputation of a state civil servant. is to define targeted measures.

Continuing his thoughts, he interprets disciplinary proceedings as a set of organizational and legal measures conducted by authorized officials in order to determine the causes and conditions of a disciplinary violation and to determine the responsible persons in accordance with the law and departmental normative legal documents[14]. This explanation of the service check can be evaluated as a relatively complete explanation.

The scientific view put forward by M.B. Dobrobaba is similar to the next definition given by N.A. Ovchinnikov. In particular, according to his opinion [15], the service inspection is an administrative-legal procedure established by law, which is a procedural process aimed at determining the violation of discipline or protecting the interests of the state civil servant, including comprehensive,

complete and truthful studies. This definition does not include the decision made as a result of disciplinary proceedings and procedural actions based on the instructions given on behalf of the head of the authorized body.

E. L. Leshchina gave a more complete description of the service inspection based on the mentioned points. According to it, the service inspection consists of developing proposals for the purpose of determining whether there is a violation of service prohibitions, discipline, and obligations of the authorized subjects, as defined by law, clarifying the situation, determining the reasons and conditions for the commission of a disciplinary act, and determining punishment measures against the guilty. It is a coercive activity interpreted on the basis of procedural law norms [16].

Based on the given definitions, the following signs of service inspection can be distinguished:

- procedural institute;
- a type of law enforcement activity;
- administrative-legal procedure;
- a set of organizational and legal actions and measures;
- handling of disciplinary violations;
- it is conducted to determine the causes and circumstances of the violation of discipline and the culprits.

In addition to the above, there are also the following special aspects of the service inspection, in particular, it provides for the use of coercive measures, the procedure is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by the legal documents, and the internal departmental inspection conducted in relation to the subordinate employee has the form specified by the legal documents.

REFERENCES

1. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language "X"//Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi-B.395;

2. n.ziyouz.com/Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language "T"//Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi-B.56;

3. n.ziyouz.com/Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language "T"//Institute of language and literature named after Alisher Navoi of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan-B.71;

4. <https://web.archive.org/web/20090528042224/> - Disciplinary production;

5. Bakhrakh D. N. Administrativnoe pravo Rossii: uchebnik. M. : Eksmo, 2011. S. 612–613.;

6. Dobrobaba M. B. Problemy extrajudicial discipline production in service law // Administrative procedure and procedure. 2015. No. 7. S. 20–21.;

7. Protasov V. N. Teoriya gosudarstva i prava : uchebnoe posobie dlya vuzov. 5-e izd., pererab. i dop. M. : Yurayt, 2020. S. 119.;

8. Kaplunov A. I. Razvitie teorii administrativnogo protsessa kak uslovie sovershenstvovaniya normativnoy osnovy administrativnogo protsessualnoy deyatel'nosti // Ugolovno-ispolnitel'noe pravo. 2017. T. 12 (1–4). No. 4. S. 494.;

9. General military regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan/"East" - Tashkent-2004;

10. Adushkin Yu. S. Disciplinarnaya otvetstvennost v USSR / pod ed. V. M. Manokhina. Saratov: Izd-vo Sarat. flour, 1986. S. 87–88.;

11. Nikonorov E. A. Institut sluzhebnoy proverki v administrativnom prave: autoref. dis. candy. walk science M., 2006. S. 12.;

12. Channov S. E. Provedenie sluzhebnoy checker na gosudarstvennoy grajdanskoy sluzhbe // Citizen and Pravo. 2008. No. 5. S. 63.;

13. Ovchinnikov N. A. Sluzhebnyaya proofka kak sposob obespecheniya zakonnosti i discipliny v deyatelnosti sotrudnikov organov vnutrennix del // Administrativnoe i municipalnoe pravo. 2011. No. 2 (38). S. 53.;

14. Ovchinnikov N. A. Sluzhebnyaya proofka kak sposob obespecheniya zakonnosti i discipliny v deyatelnosti sotrudnikov organov vnutrennix del // Administrativnoe i municipalnoe pravo. 2011. No. 2 (38). S. 54.;

15. Dobrobaba M. B. Problemy extrajudicial disciplinary production in service law//Administrative law and procedure. 2015. No. 7. S. 20-24.;

16. Leshchina E. L. Institut sluzhebnoy proverki v proizvodstve po disciplinarnym delam gosudarstvennykh slujashchix // Aktualnye problemy rossiyskogo prava. — 2021. — T. 16. — No. 9. — S. 21-29.

1. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати “Х”//Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар Академияси Алишер Навоий номидаги тил ва адабиёт институти-Б.395;

2. n.ziyouz.com/Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати “Т”//Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар Академияси Алишер Навоий номидаги тил ва адабиёт институти-Б.56;

3. n.ziyouz.com/Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати “Т”//Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар Академияси Алишер Навоий номидаги тил ва адабиёт институти-Б.71;

4. <https://web.archive.org/web/20090528042224/> - Дисциплинарное производство;

5. Бахрах Д. Н. Административное право России : учебник. М. : Эксмо, 2011. С. 612–613.;

6. Добробаба М. Б. Проблемы внесудебного дисциплинарного производства в служебном праве // Административное право и процесс. 2015. № 7. С. 20–21.;

7. Протасов В. Н. Теория государства и права : учебное пособие для вузов. 5-е изд., перераб. и доп. М. : Юрайт, 2020. С. 119.;

8. Каплунов А. И. Развитие теории административного процесса как условие совершенствования нормативной основы административно-процессуальной деятельности // Уголовно-исполнительное право. 2017. Т. 12 (1–4). № 4. С. 494.;

9. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қуролли Қучларининг Умумҳарбий низомлари/“Шарқ” – Тошкент-2004 й.;

10. Адушкин Ю. С. Дисциплинарная ответственность в СССР / под ред. В. М. Манохина. Саратов : Изд-во Саратов. ун-та, 1986. С. 87–88.;

11. Никоноров Е. А. Институт служебной проверки в административном праве : автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. М., 2006. С. 12.;

12. Чаннов С. Е. Проведение служебной проверки на государственной гражданской службе // Гражданин и право. 2008. № 5. С. 63.;

13. Овчинников Н. А. Служебная проверка как способ обеспечения законности и дисциплины в деятельности сотрудников органов внутренних дел // Административное и муниципальное право. 2011. № 2 (38). С. 53.;

14. Овчинников Н. А. Служебная проверка как способ обеспечения законности и дисциплины в деятельности сотрудников органов внутренних дел // Административное и муниципальное право. 2011. № 2 (38). С. 54.;

15. Добробаба М. Б. Проблемы внесудебного дисциплинарного производства в служебном праве//Административное право и процесс. 2015. № 7. С. 20–24.;

16. Лещина Э. Л. Институт служебной проверки в производстве по дисциплинарным делам государственных служащих // Актуальные проблемы российского права. — 2021. — Т. 16. — № 9. — С. 21– 29.

